

Supplementary information

Occurrence, fate and related health risks of PFAS in raw and produced drinking water

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13 **Quantification and quality control**

14 Identification and confirmation of target compounds were achieved by: firstly accurate mass
15 measurements of the protonated and deprotonated molecular ions within a mass window of
16 2 ppm; secondly retention time match (≤ 0.20 min) of analytes detected in samples with
17 corresponding standards in calibration solution; thirdly match between one fragment or product
18 ions of analytes acquired previously identified in calibration standard solution and those
19 determined in samples. Thus, the acquisition of a high-resolution precursor ion in combination
20 with at least one product ion and the LC relative retention time met more than the criteria
21 requirement of 5 identification points for the HR-MSMS instrumentation. List of all target
22 analytes, their exact mass, and product ion used for confirmation are shown in Table S1.

23 The branched isomers for (PFOS, PFHxS, EtFOSAA, MeFOSAA) were investigated and used
24 branched isomers standard for quantification. For PFOA and PFHpS were investigated using the
25 linear standard for the quantification (semi-quantification). No branched isomers were detected
26 for other PFAS. All branched isomers were reported as the sum of all branched isomers for each
27 of 6 PFAS.

28 Each batch of samples, three procedural blanks (Milli-Q water) were extracted simultaneously
29 and analysed for assessing the background contamination introduced and originating throughout
30 the extraction from various sources in the laboratory. One quality control sample (Milli-Q water
31 spiked with native standards) was also extracted and analysed in order to simultaneously
32 evaluate the repeatability of the analytical method and investigate any systematic errors.

33 Quantification of the targeted analytes was based on internal calibration with its corresponding
34 mass-labeled standard. For compounds that have no corresponding labelled analog standard, a
35 mass-labeled standard with similar function group and contiguous carbon-chain length was used
36 (Table S1). Methanol injections were carried out after and before the standard injection to assess
37 any carryover or contamination in the LC system.

38 An isolator column (Waters Corporation Milford, USA) had been installed after the solvent
 39 mixer of the LC pump before the sample injector to separate any contamination
 40 associated/originating from the LC system.

Chromatographic column	Mobile phase	Additives	Ion source
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kinetex F5 • Biphenyl • Mixed-mode WAX • CSH C18 column 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Methanol (MeOH) • Acetonitrile (ACN) • Mixture MeOH + ACN 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ammonium acetate • Acetic acid • Ammonia solution • 1-methylpiperidine 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electro Spray Ionization (ESI) • Ion Booster Electro Spray Ionization (IB-ESI)

Figure S1. Schematic of the experimental study design for chromatographic and ionization optimization

Figure S2. Average recoveries of mass-labeled standard in all water samples. Error bar indicates the standard deviation.

41
 42 **Figure S3.** The response of 1 ng mass labeled standard in the drinking water extract extracted with different sorbent
 43 sizes used during extraction (weak anion exchange; WAX) 250 mg and 60 mg, as compared with pure solvent
 44

Figure S4. Relative contribution per PFAS class. PFAS class: ultrashort chain PFAS (C2-C3), PFCA: perfluorocarboxylic acids (C4-C14) PFSA: perfluorosulfonic acids (C4-C10), Prec: variety of precursors (C4-C24)

45 **Figure S5.** Removal efficiencies (%) in drinking water originated from surface water treated using advanced method (GAC,
 46 PAC, UV/GAC, Ozone/GAC, or RO) for chain length (C4-C10) for perfluoro-carboxylic acids (PFCA) and perfluoro-sulfonic
 47 acids (PFSA).

48 **Table S1.** Information about the analytical standards, and the method limit of detection (LOD).

PFAS class	Compound	Acronym	Formula	Exact mass	Mass-labeled	Product ion	LOD (ng/L)	Accuracy
Ultrashort chain	Trifluoroacetic acid	TFA	C ₂ HF ₃ O ₂	113,992867	M4PFBA	CF ₃	35.44	78%
	Pentafluoropropionic acid	PFPrA	C ₃ HF ₅ O ₂	163,98967	M4PFBA	C ₂ F ₅	0.23	80%
	Perfluoropropanesulfonic acid	PFPrS	C ₃ HF ₇ O ₃ S	249,953463	M3PFBS	SO ₃	0.04	114%
	Potassium pentafluoroethanesulfonate	PFEtS	C ₂ HF ₅ O ₃ S	199,95665	M3PFBS	SO ₃ ; FSO ₃	0.04	112%
perfluorocarboxylic acids	Perfluorobutyric acid	PFBA	C ₄ HF ₇ O ₂	213,986476	M4PFBA	C ₃ F ₇	0.05	110%
	Perfluoropentanoic acid	PFPeA	C ₅ HF ₉ O ₂	263,983276	M5PFPeA	C ₄ F ₉	0.05	95%
	Perfluorohexanoic acid	PFHxA	C ₆ HF ₁₁ O ₂	313,980103	M5PFHxA	C ₅ F ₁₁	0.05	105%
	Perfluoroheptanoic acid	PFHpA	C ₇ HF ₁₃ O ₂	363,976898	M4PFHpA	C ₆ F ₁₃	0.05	101%
	Perfluorooctanoic acid	L-PFOA	C ₈ HF ₁₅ O ₂	413,973694	M8PFOA	C ₈ F ₁₅ O ₂	0.05	92%
		Br-PFOA	C ₈ HF ₁₅ O ₃	413,973694	M8PFOA	C ₈ F ₁₅ O ₂	0.05	-
	Perfluorononanoic acid	PFNA	C ₉ HF ₁₇ O ₂	463,97052	M9PFNA	C ₈ F ₁₇	0.05	93%
	Perfluorodecanoic acid	PFDA	C ₁₀ HF ₁₉ O ₂	497,972412	M6PFDA	C ₉ F ₁₉	0.05	90%
	Perfluoroundecanoic acid	PFUdA	C ₁₁ HF ₂₁ O ₂	563,964111	M7PFUdA	C ₁₀ F ₂₁	0.05	83%

perfluorosulfonic acids	Perfluorododecanoic acid	PFDoA	C ₁₂ HF ₂₃ O ₂	613,960938	MPPDoA	C12F23O2	0.05	86%
	Perfluorotridecanoic acid	PFTrDA	C ₁₃ HF ₂₅ O ₂	663,957764	M7PFUDa	C13F25O2	0.05	82%
	Perfluorotetradecanoic acid	PFTeDA	C ₁₄ HF ₂₇ O ₂	713,954529	M7PFUDa	C14F27O2	0.05	102%
	Potassium perfluoro-1-butanesulfonate	PFBS	C ₄ HF ₉ O ₃ S	299,950256	M3PFBS	FSO3;SO3	44	82%
	Sodium perfluoro-1-pentanesulfonate	PFPeS	C ₅ HF ₁₁ O ₃ S	349,947083	M3PFBS	FSO3;SO3	47	91%
	Potassium perfluorohexanesulfonate	L-PFHxS	C ₆ HF ₁₃ O ₃ S	399,943878	M3PFHxS	FSO3;SO3	37	105%
		Br-PFHxS	C ₆ HF ₁₃ O ₃ S	399,943878	M3PFHxS	FSO3;SO3	9	108%
	Sodium perfluoro-1-heptanesulfonate	L-PFHpS	C ₇ HF ₁₅ O ₃ S	449,940674	M3PFHxS	FSO3;SO3	0.05	96%
		Br-PFHpS	C ₇ HF ₁₅ O ₃ S	449,940674	M3PFHxS	FSO3;SO3	0.05	-
	Potassium perfluorooctanesulfonate	L-PFOS	C ₈ HF ₁₇ O ₃ S	499,9375	M8PFOS	FSO3;SO3	0.04	108%
		Br-PFOS	C ₈ HF ₁₇ O ₃ S	499,9375	M8PFOS	FSO3;SO3	0.01	105%
	Sodium perfluoro-1-nonanesulfonate	PFNS	C ₉ HF ₁₉ O ₃ S	549,934326	M8PFOS	FSO3;SO3	0.05	99%
	Sodium perfluoro-1-decanesulfonate	PFDS	C ₁₀ HF ₂₁ O ₃ S	599,931091	M8PFOS	FSO3;SO3	0.05	93%
	Precursors	Perfluorobutylsulphonamide	FBSA	C ₄ H ₂ F ₉ NO ₂ S	298,966248	M3PFBS	NO2S	0.05
Perfluorohexanesulfonamide		FHxSA	C ₆ H ₂ F ₁₃ NO ₂ S	398,959869	M3PFHxS	NO2S	0.05	75%
Perfluorooctanesulfonamide		FOSA	C ₈ H ₂ F ₁₇ NO ₂ S	498,953491	M8PFOS	NO2S	0.05	85%
2,3,3,3-Tetrafluoro-2-(1,1,2,2,3,3,3-heptafluoropropoxy)propanoic acid		HFPO-DA	C ₆ HF ₁₁ O ₃	329,975006	M3HFPO-DA	C3F7	0.05	98%
N-methylperfluorooctane sulfonamidoacetic acid		L-MeFOSAA	C ₁₁ H ₆ F ₁₇ NO ₄ S	570,974609	d5-N-EtFOSAA	C8F17	0.04	93%
		Br-MeFOSAA	C ₁₁ H ₆ F ₁₇ NO ₄ S	570,974609	d5-N-EtFOSAA	C8F17	0.02	84%
N-ethylperfluorooctane sulfonamidoacetic acid		L-EtFOSAA	C ₁₂ H ₈ F ₁₇ NO ₄ S	584,990234	d5-N-EtFOSAA	C8F17	0.04	95%
		Br-EtFOSAA	C ₁₂ H ₈ F ₁₇ NO ₄ S	584,990234	d5-N-EtFOSAA	C8F17	0.01	93%
Sodium 1H, 1 H,2H,2H-perfluoro-1-hexanesulfonate		4:2FTS	C ₆ H ₅ F ₉ O ₃ S	327,981567	M2-4:2FTS	C5H3F6	0.05	107%
Sodium 1 H, 1 H,2H,2H-perfluoro-1-octanesulfonate		6:2FTS	C ₈ H ₅ F ₁₃ O ₃ S	427,975189	M2-6:2FTS	C7HF8;C7F7	0.05	98%
Sodium 1 H, 1 H,2H,2H-perfluoro-1-decanesulfonate	8:2FTS	C ₁₀ H ₅ F ₁₇ O ₃ S	527,968811	M2-8:2FTS	C9HF12	0.05	90%	
Sodium dodecafluoro-3H-4,8-dioxananoate	ADONA	C ₇ H ₂ F ₁₂ O ₄	376,968322	M8PFOA	C4F9O2	0.05	100%	
Potassium 9-chlorohexadecafluoro-3-oxanonane-1-sulfonate	9Cl-PF3ONS	C ₈ HCIF ₁₆ O ₄ S	531,902858	M8PFOA	C8F12ClO	0.05	92%	

Potassium 11-chloroeicosafluoro-3-oxaundecane-1-sulfonate	11Cl-PF3OUDS	C ₁₀ ClF ₂₀ HO ₄ S	631,896471	M8PFOA	C8F20ClO	0.05	96%
Perfluoro-4-oxapentanoic acid	PF4OPeA	C ₄ HF ₇ O ₃	229,981384	M4PFBA	CF3O	0.05	94%
Perfluoro-5-oxahexanoic acid	PF5OHxA	C ₅ HF ₉ O ₃	279,97821	M3PFHxS	CF3O	0.05	97%
Perfluoro-3,6-dioxaheptanoic acid	3-6-OPFHpA	C ₅ HF ₉ O ₄	295,973114	M8PFOA	CF3O	0.05	88%
Potassium perfluoro(2-ethoxyethane)sulfonate	PFEESA	C ₄ F ₉ HO ₄ S	315,94519	M3PFHxS	CF3O	0.05	106%
Sodium 1 H, 1 H,2H,2H-perfluorododecanesulfonate	10:2FTS	C ₁₂ H ₅ F ₂₁ O ₃ S	627,962402	M2-8:2FTS	C12H3F20SO3	0.05	96%
N-(3-dimethylaminopropan-1-yl)perfluoro-1-hexanesulfonamide	N-AP-FHxSA	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ F ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂ S	484,049011	M8PFOS		0.05	96%
N-(carboxymethyl)-N,N-dimethyl-N-[3-(1H,1H,2H,2H-perfluoro-1-octanesulfonamido)propan-1-yl]ammonium	N-CMAmp-6:2FOSA	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ F ₁₃ N ₂ O ₄ S	570,085815	M8PFOS		0.05	97%
Potassium perfluoro-4-ethylcyclohexanesulfonate	PFECHS	C ₈ HF ₁₅ O ₃ S	461,940674	M8PFOA	C8F15;FSO3	0.05	97%
3-Perfluoropropyl propanoic acid (3:3)	4:2FTA	C ₆ H ₅ F ₇ O ₂	242,017776	M2-6:2FTA		0.05	97%
3-Perfluoropentyl propanoic acid (5:3)	6:2FTA	C ₈ H ₅ F ₁₁ O ₂	342,011383	M2-6:2FTA		0.05	95%
3-Perfluoroheptyl propanoic acid (7:3)	8:2FTA	C ₁₀ H ₅ F ₁₅ O ₂	442,005005	M2-8:2FTA		0.1	98%
Sodium bis(perfluorohexyl)phosphinate	6:6PFPI	C ₁₂ HF ₂₆ O ₂ P	701,929871	M5PFHxA	C6F14O2P	0.2	-
Sodium perfluorohexylperfluorooctylphosphinate	6:8PFPI	C ₁₄ HF ₃₀ O ₂ P	801,923523	M8PFOA		0.2	-
Sodium bis(perfluorooctyl)phosphinate	8:8PFPI	C ₁₆ HF ₃₄ O ₂ P	901,917114	M8PFOA		0.2	-
Sodium 1H,1H,2H,2H-perfluorooctylphosphate	6:2PAP	C ₈ H ₆ F ₁₃ O ₄ P	443,979614	M8PFOA	H2O4P	0.2	-
Sodium 1H,1H,2H,2H-perfluorodecylphosphate	8:2PAP	C ₁₀ H ₆ F ₁₇ O ₄ P	543,973206	M8PFOA	H2O4P	0.2	-
Sodium bis(1H,1H,2H,2H-perfluorooctyl)phosphate	6:2diPAP	C ₁₆ H ₉ F ₂₆ O ₄ P	789,9823	M8PFOA	H2O4P	0.2	72%
Sodium bis(1H,1H,2H,2H-perfluorodecyl)phosphate	8:2diPAP	C ₂₀ H ₉ F ₃₄ O ₄ P	989,969543	M8PFOA	C10H5F17O4P	0.2	-
N-ethylperfluoro-1-octanesulfonamidoacetic acid	N-EtFOSA	C ₁₀ H ₆ F ₁₇ NO ₂ S	526,984802	d9-N-EtFOSE	C3F7	0.05	104%
N-methylperfluoro-1-octanesulfonamidoacetic acid	N-MeFOSA	C ₉ H ₄ F ₁₇ NO ₂ S	512,969116	d3-N-MeFOSA	C3F7	0.05	93%
2-(N-ethylperfluoro-1-octanesulfonamido)-ethanol	N-EtFOSE	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ F ₁₇ NO ₃ S	571,010986	d3-N-MeFOSA	C2H3O2	0.05	98%

2-(N-methylperfluoro-1-octanesulfonamido)-ethanol	N-MeFOSE	$C_{11}H_8F_{17}NO_3S$	556,995361	d9-N-EtFOSE	$C_2H_3O_2$	0.05	98%
N-(methyl) nonafluorobutanesulfonamide	MeFBSA	$C_5H_4F_9NO_2S$	312,981903	M3PFBS	NO_3S	0.05	97%
Perfluoro-n-[^{13}C]butanoic acid	M4PFBA	$^{13}C_4HF_7O_2$	219,007173				
Perfluoro-n-[^{13}C]pentanoic acid	M5PFPeA	$^{13}C_5HF_9O_2$	270,007334				
Perfluoro-n-[1,2,3,4,6- ^{13}C]hexanoic acid	M5PFHxA	$^{13}C_5CHF_{11}O_2$	320,00414				
Perfluoro-n-[1,2,3,4- ^{13}C]heptanoic acid	M4PFHpA	$^{13}C_4C_3HF_{13}O_2$	368,997592				
Perfluoro-n-[^{13}C]octanoic acid	M8PFOA	$^{13}C_8HF_{15}O_2$	423,007818				
Perfluoro-n-[^{13}C]nonanoic acid	M9PFNA	$^{13}C_9HF_{17}O_2$	474,007979				
Perfluoro-n-[1,2,3,4,5,6- ^{13}C]decanoic acid	M6PFDA	$^{13}C_6C_4HF_{19}O_2$	520,994721				
Perfluoro-n-[1,2,3,4,5,6,7- ^{13}C]undecanoic acid	M7PFUdA	$^{13}C_7C_4HF_{21}O_2$	571,994882				
Perfluoro-n-[1,2- ^{13}C]dodecanoic acid	MPFDoA	$^{13}C_2C_{10}HF_{23}O_2$	616,974914				
2,3,3,3-Tetrafluoro-2-(1,1,2,2,3,3,3-heptafluoropropoxy)- ^{13}C -propanoic acid	M3HFPO-DA	$^{13}C_3C_3HF_{11}O_3$	333,992345				
Sodium perfluoro-1-[2,3,4- ^{13}C]butanesulfonate	M3PFBS	$^{13}C_3CHF_9O_3S$	303,96761				
Sodium perfluoro-1-[1,2,3- ^{13}C]hexanesulfonate	M3PFHxS	$^{13}C_3C_3H_2F_{13}O_3S$	404,969048				
Sodium perfluoro-1-[^{13}C]octanesulfonate	M8PFOS	$^{13}C_8HF_{17}O_3S$	508,97161				
Sodium 1 H, 1 H,2H,2H-perfluoro-1-[1,2- ^{13}C]hexanesulfonate	M2-4:2FTS	$^{13}C_2C_4H_5F_9O_3S$	330,995555				
Sodium 1 H, 1 H,2H,2H-perfluoro-1-[1,2- ^{13}C]octanesulfonate	M2-6:2FTS	$^{13}C_2C_6H_5F_{13}O_3S$	430,989168				
Sodium 1 H, 1 H,2H,2H-perfluoro-1-[1,2- ^{13}C]decanesulfonate	M2-8:2FTS	$^{13}C_2C_8H_5F_{17}O_3S$	530,982781				
2-Perfluorohexyl-[1,2- ^{13}C]-ethanoic acid	M2-6:2FTA	$^{13}C_2C_6H_3F_{13}O_2$	381,006532				
2-Perfluorooctyl-[1,2- ^{13}C]-ethanoic acid	M2-8:2FTA	$^{13}C_2C_8H_3F_{17}O_2$	481,000145				
2-Perfluorodecyl-[1,2- ^{13}C]-ethanoic acid	M2-10:2FTA	$^{13}C_2C_{10}H_3F_{21}O_2$	580,993758				
Sodium bis(1 H, 1 H,2H,2H-[1,2- ^{13}C]perfluorooctyl)phosphate	M4-6:2diPAP	$^{13}C_4C_{12}H_9F_{26}O_4P$	795,003025				
Sodium bis(1 H, 1 H,2H,2H-[1,2- ^{13}C]perfluorodecyl)phosphate	M4-8:2diPAP	$^{13}C_4C_{16}H_9F_{34}O_4P$	994,990251				
N-methyl- d_3 -perfluoro-1-octanesulfonamide	d_3 -MeFOSA	$2^3H_3C_9HF_{17}NO_2S$	516,995236				

Injection standard	2-(N-ethyl-d ₅ -perfluoro-1-octanesulfonamido)ethan-d ₄ -ol	d ₉ -N-EtFOSE	² H ₉ C ₁₂ HF ₁₇ NO ₃ S	581,074761
	N-Ethyl-n-perfluorooctanesulfonamidoacetic acid-d ₅	d ₅ -N-EtFOSAA	² H ₅ C ₁₂ H ₃ F ₁₇ N ₀ O ₄ S	591,028919
	Perfluoro-n-[2,3,4- ¹³ C ₃]butanoic acid	M3PFBA	¹³ C ₃ CHF ₇ O ₂	218,003818
	Perfluoro-n-(1,2- ¹³ C ₂)octanoic acid	M2PFOA	¹³ C ₂ C ₆ HF ₁₅ O ₂	416,987689
	Sodium perfluoro-1-[1,2,3,4- ¹³ C ₄]octanesulfonate	M4PFOS	¹³ C ₄ C ₄ HF ₁₇ O ₃ S	504,95819
	N-ethyl-d ₅ -perfluoro-1-octanesulfonamide	d ₅ -N-EtFOSA-M	² H ₅ C ₁₀ HF ₁₇ NO ₂ S	533,023439
	2-(N-methyl-d ₃ -perfluoro-1-octanesulfonamido)ethan-d ₄ -ol	d ₇ -N-MeFOSE-M	² H ₇ C ₁₁ HF ₁₇ NO ₃ S	565,046558
	N-Methyl-n-perfluorooctanesulfonamidoacetic acid-d ₃	N-MeFOSAA-d ₃	² H ₃ C ₁₁ H ₃ F ₁₇ N ₀ O ₄ S	575,000715

49

50 **Table S2.** Relative potency factors (RPF) for PFAS reported in the Bil et al and Rietjens et al studies and used to
51 calculate the perfluorooctanoic acid equivalent (PEQ).

	<i>RPF (BIL ET AL., 2021)</i>	<i>RPF (BIL ET AL., 2022)</i>	<i>RPF (RIETJENS ET AL, 2021)</i>
FBS	0,001	0,023	0,008
PFPEs	0,001 ≤ RPF ≤ 0,6	-	-
PFHXS	0,6	0,91	0,24
PFHPS	0,6 ≤ RPF ≤ 2	-	-
PFOS	2	2,6	1,5
PFDS	2	-	-
PFBA	0,05	-	-
PFPEA	0,01 ≤ RPF ≤ 0,05	-	-
PFHXA	0,01	0,011	0,003
PFHPA	0,01 ≤ RPF ≤ 1	-	-
PFOA	1	1	1
PFNA	10	7,2	1,5
PFDA	4 ≤ RPF ≤ 10	5,9	2,9
PFUNDA	4	-	-
PFDODA	3	-	-
PFTRDA	0,3 ≤ RPF ≤ 3	-	-
PFTEDA	0,3	-	-
PFHXDA	0,02	-	-
PFODA	0,02	-	-
HFPO-DA	0,06	-	-
ADONA	0,03	-	-

52

53 **Table S3.** Results per individual PFAS and location. The concentration in ngg/L. AV, and SD represent the average
54 and standard deviation of the triplicate analysis, respectively.

Surface water

	1		2				3				4				5				6					
	DW-1		RW-1		DW-2		RW-2		DW-3		RW-3		DW-4		RW-4		DW-5		RW-5		DW-6		RW-6	
	AV	ST	AV	ST	AV	ST	AV	ST	AV	ST	AV	ST												
<i>TFA</i>	296.24	10.26	106.07	0.49	377.42	26.64	263.88	3.34	359.86	17.56	154.60	1.33	381.44	19.11	133.90	1.47	1104.60	211.08	131.56	1.57	477.05	31.68	144.00	4.09
<i>PFPrA</i>	63.70	3.84	<LOD	0.00	41.52	1.45	<LOD	0.00	65.55	8.19	<LOD	0.00	64.45	12.15	<LOD	0.00	16.74	0.70	<LOD	0.00	22.22	4.96	1.04	0.14
<i>PFPrS</i>	0.17	0.01	0.13	0.00	0.20	0.00	0.09	0.00	0.16	0.01	0.11	0.01	0.16	0.00	0.11	0.00	0.08	0.01	0.10	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.07	0.00
<i>PFETs</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00												
<i>Σultrashort</i>	360.11	0.00	106.20	0.00	419.14	0.00	263.97	0.00	425.57	0.00	154.71	0.00	446.04	0.00	134.01	0.00	1121.43	0.00	131.66	0.00	499.33	0.00	145.12	0.00
<i>PFBA</i>	10.18	0.57	5.61	0.56	13.41	0.30	7.98	1.40	8.05	0.21	3.90	0.18	10.82	1.20	8.47	0.46	4.35	0.32	3.59	0.09	3.60	0.31	5.12	0.44
<i>PFPeA</i>	6.89	0.39	4.47	0.11	3.96	0.03	2.44	0.18	5.44	0.13	3.46	0.06	6.65	0.40	3.97	0.18	4.27	0.24	3.26	0.09	3.31	0.27	4.66	0.32
<i>PFHxA</i>	8.80	1.64	6.19	0.34	7.60	0.01	3.66	0.19	6.85	0.34	4.31	0.20	7.61	0.37	5.41	0.19	4.62	0.06	4.97	0.15	3.34	0.19	5.94	0.11
<i>PFHpA</i>	5.68	0.62	4.22	0.06	2.59	0.05	1.66	0.03	4.74	0.23	2.76	0.06	5.05	0.22	3.59	0.13	2.63	0.09	2.47	0.06	2.01	0.06	3.90	0.29
<i>L-PFOA</i>	3.63	0.07	4.56	0.07	2.23	0.06	2.44	0.05	6.68	0.05	5.36	0.12	7.17	0.35	7.12	0.42	3.19	0.12	3.80	0.15	2.52	0.10	32.97	5.69
<i>Br-PFOA</i>	0.93	0.01	0.86	0.03	0.50	0.02	0.38	0.01	1.21	0.01	0.87	0.01	1.52	0.37	1.37	0.07	0.36	0.03	0.36	0.02	0.37	0.15	4.24	0.12
<i>ΣPFOA</i>	4.55	0.00	5.42	0.00	2.73	0.00	2.82	0.00	7.89	0.00	6.23	0.00	8.70	0.00	8.48	0.00	3.55	0.00	4.17	0.00	2.89	0.00	37.21	0.00
<i>PFNA</i>	0.30	0.01	0.40	0.01	0.20	0.01	0.41	0.00	0.40	0.02	0.35	0.02	0.26	0.02	0.33	0.02	0.36	0.00	0.47	0.01	0.29	0.01	0.75	0.06
<i>PFDA</i>	0.17	0.02	0.22	0.00	0.05	0.00	0.24	0.00	0.30	0.00	0.21	0.01	0.15	0.01	0.27	0.02	0.18	0.02	0.28	0.01	0.14	0.01	0.34	0.12
<i>PFUdA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.07	0.00	<LOD	0.00												
<i>PFDoA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00												
<i>PFTrDA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00												
<i>PFTeDA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00												
<i>ΣPFCA</i>	36.57	0.00	31.93	0.00	30.55	0.00	22.03	0.00	33.66	0.00	27.45	0.00	39.23	0.00	38.99	0.00	19.96	0.00	23.37	0.00	15.65	0.00	95.13	0.00
<i>PFBS</i>	2.34	0.12	1.76	0.04	3.39	0.06	2.13	0.01	2.05	0.07	1.45	0.05	2.03	0.03	1.46	0.06	1.69	0.04	1.17	0.01	1.17	0.04	1.07	0.04
<i>PFPeS</i>	0.34	0.02	0.34	0.02	0.35	0.01	0.28	0.01	0.42	0.01	0.29	0.01	0.40	0.02	0.38	0.02	0.23	0.01	0.25	0.01	0.18	0.02	0.23	0.01
<i>L-PFHxS</i>	1.59	0.03	1.68	0.01	0.58	0.02	1.02	0.01	2.03	0.05	1.50	0.04	2.59	0.09	2.39	0.09	0.61	0.03	0.81	0.01	0.63	0.21	0.74	0.02
<i>Br-PFHxS</i>	0.49	0.01	0.40	0.01	0.28	0.01	0.26	0.01	0.53	0.01	0.41	0.01	0.68	0.01	0.57	0.03	0.13	0.01	0.22	0.00	0.15	0.08	0.22	0.01
<i>ΣPFHxS</i>	2.08	0.00	2.08	0.00	0.85	0.00	1.28	0.00	2.57	0.00	1.90	0.00	3.27	0.00	2.96	0.00	0.74	0.00	1.03	0.00	0.78	0.00	0.96	0.00
<i>PFHpS</i>	<LOD	0.00	0.09	0.00	0.05	0.00	0.07	0.00	0.08	0.00	0.08	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.09	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.07	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.07	0.00
<i>Br-PFHpS</i>	<LOD	0.01	0.05	0.02	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.05	0.00	<LOD	0.01	0.05	0.01	0.05	0.01	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.01

<i>ΣPFHpS</i>	<LOD	0.00	0.14	0.00	0.05	0.00	0.07	0.00	0.13	0.00	0.08	0.00	0.11	0.00	0.14	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.07	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.07	0.00
<i>L-PFOS</i>	1.66	0.15	3.12	0.00	0.35	0.03	2.57	0.00	2.09	0.03	2.19	0.00	1.15	0.05	1.89	0.00	0.76	0.06	2.00	0.00	0.61	0.01	1.99	0.00
<i>Br-PFOS</i>	1.17	0.09	2.26	0.05	0.46	0.02	1.52	0.06	2.22	0.16	1.83	0.09	1.64	0.05	2.00	0.19	0.93	0.05	1.67	0.10	0.75	0.09	1.30	0.49
<i>ΣPFOS</i>	2.83	0.00	5.38	0.00	0.81	0.00	4.09	0.00	4.30	0.00	4.02	0.00	2.80	0.00	3.89	0.00	1.69	0.00	3.67	0.00	1.36	0.00	3.29	0.00
<i>PFNS</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.06	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00												
<i>PFDS</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00																
<i>ΣPFSA</i>	7.67	0.00	17.31	0.00	5.45	0.00	13.34	0.00	9.46	0.00	13.80	0.00	8.60	0.00	15.83	0.00	4.37	0.00	11.02	0.00	3.49	0.00	9.97	0.00
<i>FBSA</i>	0.32	0.03	<LOD	0.00	0.22	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.26	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.24	0.01	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.13	0.03
<i>FHxSA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00																
<i>FOSA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00																
<i>L-MeFOSAA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00																
<i>Br-MeFOSAA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00																
<i>L-EtFOSAA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00																
<i>Br-EtFOSAA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00																
<i>4:2FTS</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00																
<i>6:2FTS</i>	<LOD	0.02	0.28	0.03	0.17	0.01	0.31	0.01	0.09	0.03	0.15	0.02	0.05	0.02	0.19	0.01	0.21	0.00	1.19	0.04	0.12	0.02	0.16	0.02
<i>8:2FTS</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00																
<i>ADONA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00																
<i>9Cl-PF3ONS</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00																
<i>11Cl-PF3OUDS</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00																
<i>PF4OPeA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00																
<i>PF5OHxA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00																
<i>3-6-OPFHpA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00																
<i>PFEESA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00																
<i>10:2FTS</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00																
<i>PFECHS</i>	0.48	0.01	0.64	0.06	0.13	0.00	0.47	0.04	1.11	0.00	1.13	0.03	1.40	0.05	1.74	0.14	0.18	0.01	0.42	0.02	0.16	0.02	0.46	0.03
<i>4:2FTA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00																
<i>6:2FTA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00																

8:2FTA	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00														
6:2diPAP	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00														
6:6PPPi	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00														
8:2PAP	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00														
EtFOSA	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00														
MeFOSA	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00														
MeFOSE	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00														
EtFOSE	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00														
PFHO-DA	0.55	0.00	0.35	0.00	0.11	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.78	0.00	0.42	0.00	0.65	0.00	0.35	0.00	0.46	0.00	0.44	0.00	0.40	0.00	19.03	0.00
ΣPrec	1.39	0.00	1.26	0.00	0.63	0.00	0.78	0.00	2.24	0.00	1.70	0.00	2.35	0.00	2.27	0.00	0.87	0.00	2.05	0.00	0.69	0.00	19.78	0.00
Total PFAS	405.74	0.00	156.70	0.00	455.76	0.00	300.11	0.00	470.93	0.00	197.65	0.00	496.21	0.00	191.10	0.00	1146.63	0.00	168.10	0.00	519.15	0.00	270.00	0.00

Surface water

Groundwater

	7												8				9				10				11				12			
	DW-7		RW-7		DW-8		RW-8		DW-9		RW-9		DW-10		RW-10		DW-11		RW-11		DW-12		RW-12									
	AV	ST	AV	ST	AV	ST	AV	ST	AV	ST	AV	ST	AV	ST	AV	ST	AV	ST	AV	ST	AV	ST	AV	ST								
TFA	645.90	104.13	641.34	0.35	94.03	22.71	126.01	0.42	33.56	4.05	189.69	1.53	44.95	22.74	135.15	0.00	54.38	20.12	82.44	1.94	134.04	20.02	87.77	0.11								
PFPrA	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	11.14	0.67	2.18	0.70	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	5.80	4.21	<LOD	0.00	1.14	0.00	<LOD	0.00	9.78	2.21	1.41	0.08								
PFPrS	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.14	0.01	0.07	0.01	0.08	0.01	<LOD	0.00	0.09	0.01	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.07	0.00								
PFEtS	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00								
Σultrshort	645.90	0.00	641.34	0.00	105.31	0.00	128.25	0.00	33.64	0.00	189.69	0.00	50.84	0.00	135.15	0.00	55.52	0.00	82.44	0.00	143.82	0.00	89.25	0.00								
PFBA	1.27	0.01	2.54	0.45	12.28	1.12	14.06	1.53	3.49	0.71	4.81	0.56	4.46	0.57	3.25	0.00	7.90	0.38	14.95	0.00	0.43	0.26	2.62	0.29								
PFPeA	0.29	0.08	<LOD	0.00	3.75	0.11	2.68	0.08	0.52	0.01	0.95	0.11	2.20	0.04	1.90	0.00	1.18	0.05	2.82	0.64	<LOD	0.00	0.47	0.04								
PFHxA	0.30	0.02	1.64	0.23	3.03	0.05	2.42	0.06	0.75	0.01	1.20	0.08	1.23	0.02	1.63	0.00	0.68	0.03	2.69	0.09	<LOD	0.00	0.39	0.02								
PFHpA	0.24	0.00	1.21	0.12	1.98	0.03	1.70	0.05	0.68	0.06	0.92	0.07	0.37	0.01	0.83	0.00	0.32	0.04	1.83	0.02	<LOD	0.00	0.05	0.01								
L-PFOA	0.74	0.00	4.10	1.08	4.02	0.06	5.81	0.11	4.28	0.50	8.46	0.40	1.60	0.03	5.62	0.00	1.07	0.01	41.97	1.17	0.06	0.01	0.10	0.01								
Br-PFOA	0.09	0.00	0.30	0.01	1.28	0.30	0.81	0.01	0.77	0.07	0.88	0.01	0.35	0.01	0.42	0.00	0.34	0.01	3.85	0.12	<LOD	0.01	<LOD	0.00								
ΣPFOA	0.83	0.00	4.39	0.00	5.30	0.00	6.61	0.00	5.05	0.00	9.34	0.00	1.95	0.00	6.04	0.00	1.41	0.00	45.83	0.00	0.07	0.00	0.13	0.00								

<i>PFNA</i>	0.13	0.00	0.30	0.07	0.28	0.01	0.26	0.01	0.17	0.00	0.21	0.01	<LOD	0.00	0.09	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.42	0.01	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
<i>PFDA</i>	0.18	0.01	0.81	0.48	0.14	0.00	0.16	0.02	<LOD	0.00	0.05	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.05	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.37	0.09	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
<i>PFUdA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
<i>PFDoA</i>	<LOD	0.00	0.12	0.03	<LOD	0.00	0.16	0.02	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00												
<i>PFTrDA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
<i>PFTeDA</i>	<LOD	0.00	1.65	0.21	<LOD	0.00	3.15	1.71	<LOD	0.00	1.68	0.24	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
Σ <i>PFCA</i>	3.25	0.00	17.06	0.00	26.76	0.00	37.66	0.00	10.70	0.00	28.50	0.00	10.24	0.00	19.85	0.00	11.49	0.00	114.89	0.00	0.50	0.00	3.79	0.00
<i>PFBS</i>	0.22	0.01	0.09	0.04	3.50	0.23	5.13	0.44	1.74	0.03	2.44	0.06	1.69	0.01	5.06	0.00	0.81	0.02	19.00	0.19	0.06	0.01	0.10	0.01
<i>PFPeS</i>	0.09	0.00	0.18	0.02	0.38	0.03	0.35	0.01	0.19	0.01	0.18	0.00	0.09	0.00	0.18	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.62	0.07	0.09	0.01	0.17	0.01
<i>L-PFHxS</i>	0.15	0.00	0.52	0.00	1.76	0.03	2.03	0.04	0.38	0.03	0.43	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.41	0.00	0.04	0.00	0.63	0.01	0.04	0.00	0.06	0.00
<i>Br-PFHxS</i>	0.03	0.00	0.09	0.00	0.41	0.05	0.33	0.01	0.11	0.01	0.12	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.14	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.26	0.01	<LOD	0.00	0.03	0.00
Σ <i>PFHxS</i>	0.18	0.00	0.61	0.00	2.17	0.00	2.36	0.00	0.49	0.00	0.55	0.00	0.04	0.00	0.55	0.00	0.05	0.00	0.88	0.00	0.05	0.00	0.09	0.00
<i>PFHpS</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.13	0.05	0.08	0.00	0.05	0.05	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
<i>Br-PFHpS</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.01	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00								
Σ <i>PFHpS</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.13	0.00	0.08	0.00	0.05	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00								
<i>L-PFOS</i>	0.13	0.00	0.46	0.00	1.62	0.07	2.25	0.00	0.37	0.20	0.54	0.00	0.05	0.01	0.71	0.00	0.04	0.02	0.79	0.02	<LOD	0.01	<LOD	0.00
<i>Br-PFOS</i>	0.20	0.00	0.42	0.09	1.86	0.36	1.34	0.25	0.50	0.04	0.56	0.03	0.10	0.02	0.76	0.00	0.03	0.01	1.05	0.02	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
Σ <i>PFOS</i>	0.33	0.00	0.88	0.00	3.48	0.00	3.59	0.00	0.87	0.00	1.10	0.00	0.15	0.00	1.47	0.00	0.06	0.00	1.84	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
<i>PFNS</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
<i>PFDS</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
Σ <i>PFSA</i>	0.81	0.00	3.25	0.00	9.66	0.00	17.54	0.00	3.34	0.00	5.92	0.00	1.97	0.00	9.27	0.00	0.92	0.00	25.07	0.00	0.23	0.00	0.46	0.00
<i>FBSA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.02	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.01	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
<i>FHxSA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
<i>FOSA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
<i>L-MeFOSAA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
<i>Br-MeFOSAA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.11	0.01	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
<i>L-EtFOSAA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.07	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.32	0.03	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
<i>Br-EtFOSAA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.13	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.47	0.03	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
<i>4:2FTS</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00

6:2FTS	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.01	0.28	0.02	<LOD	0.00	0.17	0.02	<LOD	0.01	0.26	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.68	0.05	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
8:2FTS	0.17	0.00	1.58	0.39	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.08	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.42	0.04	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
ADONA	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.20	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
9Cl- PF3ONS	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
11Cl- PF3OUDS	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
PF4OPeA	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
PF5OHxA	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
3-6- OPFHpA	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.02	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
PFEESA	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
10:2FTS	0.31	0.06	4.93	1.04	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.07	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
PFECHS	0.06	0.00	0.15	0.00	0.52	0.09	0.56	0.05	0.29	0.03	0.56	0.01	<LOD	0.00	0.14	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.23	0.01	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
4:2FTA	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
6:2FTA	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
8:2FTA	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
6:2diPAP	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
6:6PFPi	<LOD	0.00	2.51	0.22	<LOD	0.00	0.79	0.02	<LOD	0.00	1.44	0.05	<LOD	0.00	0.62	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
8:2PAP	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
EtFOSA	<LOD	0.00	0.97	0.10	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
MeFOSA	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
MeFOSE	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
EtFOSE	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
PFHO-DA	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.19	0.00	9.83	0.00	9.60	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
ΣPrec	0.54	0.00	10.14	0.00	0.54	0.00	1.63	0.00	0.34	0.00	2.36	0.00	9.90	0.00	10.98	0.00	0.25	0.00	2.43	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
Total PFAS	650.51	0.00	671.79	0.00	142.27	0.00	185.09	0.00	48.02	0.00	226.47	0.00	72.95	0.00	175.25	0.00	68.18	0.00	224.83	0.00	144.56	0.00	93.50	0.00

Groundwater

	13		14				15				16				17				18					
	DW-13		RW-13		DW-14		RW-14		DW-15		RW-15		DW-16		RW-16		DW-17		RW-17		DW-18		RW-18	
	AV	ST	AV	ST	AV	ST	AV	ST	AV	ST	AV	ST	AV	ST	AV	ST	AV	ST	AV	ST	AV	ST	AV	ST
<i>TFA</i>	482.95	124.32	520.93	6.28	384.88	9.94	388.15	1.93	438.09	63.03	483.63	0.19	98.19	3.25	204.46	0.92	90.58	12.61	352.49	8.04	88.44	0.07	133.73	1.14
<i>PFPPrA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	4.90	1.96	28.39	0.69	11.13	1.18	8.99	1.27	1.67	0.33
<i>PFPPrS</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
<i>PFEtS</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
<i>Σultrshort</i>	482.95	0.00	520.93	0.00	384.88	0.00	388.15	0.00	438.09	0.00	483.63	0.00	98.19	0.00	209.36	0.00	118.97	0.00	363.62	0.00	97.43	0.00	135.40	0.00
<i>PFBA</i>	0.40	0.01	1.04	0.00	0.31	0.07	<LOD	0.00	0.13	0.03	<LOD	0.00	0.30	0.01	1.22	0.20	1.17	0.03	3.69	0.31	0.97	0.04	0.84	0.05
<i>PFPeA</i>	0.23	0.02	0.54	0.04	0.19	0.02	<LOD	0.00	0.10	0.01	0.31	0.01	<LOD	0.00	0.25	0.07	<LOD	0.00	0.33	0.04	0.30	0.01	<LOD	0.00
<i>PFHxA</i>	0.35	0.01	0.54	0.01	0.24	0.01	0.40	0.04	0.15	0.01	0.41	0.10	<LOD	0.00	0.40	0.07	<LOD	0.00	0.44	0.10	0.23	0.01	0.19	0.01
<i>PFHpA</i>	0.22	0.00	0.32	0.01	0.16	0.01	0.23	0.02	0.11	0.00	0.21	0.04	<LOD	0.00	0.26	0.07	<LOD	0.00	0.33	0.13	0.10	0.00	<LOD	0.00
<i>L-PFOA</i>	0.87	0.01	1.27	0.01	0.61	0.00	1.24	0.11	0.34	0.05	0.67	0.28	0.10	0.01	0.69	0.25	0.28	0.02	0.84	0.07	0.35	0.02	0.16	0.02
<i>Br-PFOA</i>	0.15	0.01	0.20	0.01	0.06	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.05	0.01	0.08	0.01	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.06	0.01	0.14	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
<i>ΣPFOA</i>	1.03	0.00	1.47	0.00	0.68	0.00	1.27	0.00	0.39	0.00	0.75	0.00	0.13	0.00	0.73	0.00	0.34	0.00	0.97	0.00	0.36	0.00	0.19	0.00
<i>PFNA</i>	0.09	0.00	0.10	0.00	0.08	0.00	0.05	0.01	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.02	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.06	0.00	<LOD	0.00
<i>PFDA</i>	0.08	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.28	0.00	0.64	0.05	0.15	0.00	0.18	0.08	<LOD	0.00	0.40	0.17	<LOD	0.00	0.07	0.01	0.13	0.01	<LOD	0.00
<i>PFUdA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.07	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
<i>PFDoA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.01	0.09	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.01	<LOD	0.00	0.05	0.05	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
<i>PFTTrDA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
<i>PFTeDA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.55	0.05	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
<i>ΣPFCA</i>	2.39	0.00	5.47	0.00	1.97	0.00	4.57	0.00	1.03	0.00	2.61	0.00	0.44	0.00	4.02	0.00	1.51	0.00	6.80	0.00	2.17	0.00	1.41	0.00
<i>PFBS</i>	0.12	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.05	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.07	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
<i>PFPeS</i>	0.08	0.00	0.07	0.00	0.05	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.03	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.08	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
<i>L-PFHxS</i>	0.04	0.00	0.07	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
<i>Br-PFHxS</i>	<LOD	0.00	0.04	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
<i>ΣPFHxS</i>	0.06	0.00	0.11	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
<i>PFHpS</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
<i>Br-PFHpS</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00

<i>ΣPFHps</i>	<LOD	0.00																						
<i>L-PFOS</i>	0.12	0.01	0.24	0.00	0.08	0.00	0.10	0.00	0.09	0.02	0.05	0.00	0.04	0.01	0.11	0.00	0.06	0.02	0.05	0.00	0.05	0.00	<LOD	0.00
<i>Br-PFOS</i>	0.17	0.00	0.31	0.01	0.09	0.00	0.09	0.00	0.08	0.01	0.07	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.10	0.03	0.06	0.02	0.11	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.06	0.00
<i>ΣPFOS</i>	0.29	0.00	0.54	0.00	0.16	0.00	0.20	0.00	0.17	0.00	0.13	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.21	0.00	0.12	0.00	0.16	0.00	0.07	0.00	0.06	0.00
<i>PFNS</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.02	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.01	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00												
<i>PFDS</i>	<LOD	0.00																						
<i>ΣPFSA</i>	0.55	0.00	1.38	0.00	0.26	0.00	0.39	0.00	0.23	0.00	0.25	0.00	0.10	0.00	0.42	0.00	0.19	0.00	0.39	0.00	0.11	0.00	0.12	0.00
<i>FBSA</i>	<LOD	0.00																						
<i>FHxSA</i>	<LOD	0.00																						
<i>FOSA</i>	<LOD	0.00																						
<i>L-MeFOSAA</i>	<LOD	0.00																						
<i>Br-MeFOSAA</i>	<LOD	0.00																						
<i>L-EtFOSAA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.06	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00												
<i>Br-EtFOSAA</i>	<LOD	0.00	0.06	0.08	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00												
<i>4:2FTS</i>	<LOD	0.00																						
<i>6:2FTS</i>	<LOD	0.00	0.14	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.15	0.01	0.05	0.01	<LOD	0.00	0.09	0.09	0.19	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.14	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.12	0.00
<i>8:2FTS</i>	0.11	0.00	0.21	0.02	0.21	0.01	0.92	0.21	0.18	0.00	1.03	0.05	<LOD	0.00	0.35	0.11	<LOD	0.00	0.14	0.04	0.20	0.01	<LOD	0.00
<i>ADONA</i>	<LOD	0.00																						
<i>9Cl-PF3ONS</i>	<LOD	0.00																						
<i>11Cl-PF3OUDS</i>	<LOD	0.00																						
<i>PF4OPeA</i>	<LOD	0.00																						
<i>PF5OHxA</i>	<LOD	0.00																						
<i>3-6-OPFHpA</i>	<LOD	0.00																						
<i>PFEESA</i>	<LOD	0.00																						
<i>10:2FTS</i>	0.32	0.02	0.37	0.10	0.66	0.13	1.60	0.40	0.46	0.02	1.95	0.73	<LOD	0.00	0.35	0.01	0.07	0.01	0.14	0.05	0.37	0.03	<LOD	0.00
<i>PFECHS</i>	0.05	0.00	<LOD	0.00																				
<i>4:2FTA</i>	<LOD	0.00																						
<i>6:2FTA</i>	<LOD	0.00																						

<i>8:2FTA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00										
<i>6:2diPAP</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00										
<i>6:6PPFi</i>	<LOD	0.00	0.69	0.05	<LOD	0.00	0.82	0.10	<LOD	0.00	0.83	0.14	<LOD	0.00	0.84	0.08	<LOD	0.00	0.64	0.02	<LOD	0.00	0.60	0.05
<i>8:2PAP</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00										
<i>EtFOSA</i>	<LOD	0.02	0.22	0.02	<LOD	0.00	0.39	0.18	<LOD	0.01	0.59	0.23	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00
<i>MeFOSA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00										
<i>MeFOSE</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00										
<i>EtFOSE</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00										
<i>PFHO-DA</i>	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.00										
Σ Prec	0.57	0.00	1.62	0.00	0.97	0.00	3.87	0.00	0.80	0.00	4.40	0.00	0.09	0.00	1.79	0.00	0.07	0.00	1.06	0.00	0.56	0.00	0.72	0.00
<i>Total PFAS</i>	486.47	0.00	529.40	0.00	388.08	0.00	396.98	0.00	440.15	0.00	490.90	0.00	98.82	0.00	215.59	0.00	120.74	0.00	371.88	0.00	100.26	0.00	137.65	0.00

Reference

- Bil, W., Zeilmaker, M., Fragki, S., Lijzen, J., Verbruggen, E., Bokkers, B., 2022. Response to Letter to the Editor on Bil et al. 2021 “Risk Assessment of Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substance Mixtures: A Relative Potency Factor Approach.” *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry* 41, 13–18. <https://doi.org/10.1002/etc.5236>
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